

Talking about the "People's Character" in Song Creation

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Abstract

General Secretary Xi pointed out that "Socialist literature and art are essentially people's literature and art"^①. General Secretary Xi Jinping's speech clarified the "people-oriented" nature of literary and artistic creation in the new era, and emphasized that literary and artistic creation should adhere to the people-centered literary and artistic ideology. Music creation is a kind of artistic practice, which refers to the complicated mental production labor of composers to create music with musical beauty. People's musician Shi Guangnan's song creation has a strong life atmosphere, sincere feelings, warm and cordial. "People's character" is the primary principle in his creation. He is rooted in the masses of the people, well acquainted with the aesthetic needs of the masses, and always adheres to the direction of "serving the people". The song materials are taken from the people and used by the people. The people's character of his song creation is mainly embodied in: strong national character, simple popular character, distinctive time character and strong family and country feelings. His creative ideas and his creative process all reflect the "people's character" of musicians. In the new historical period, we will continue to explore and explore the "people's character" of music creation, and continue to explore and study the "people's character" of song melody thinking with Chinese national temperament and Chinese phonology in song creation, which contributes to the healthy development of Chinese song creation. Has important epochal significance.

Introduction

President Xi Jinping, in mid-October 2014, presided over a symposium on art work and made an important speech. The public announcement of the speech provided basic documents for the in-depth study and implementation of the broad masses of party members, cadres and literary and art workers. General Secretary Xi Jinping pointed out: "There are one hundred or one thousand literary and artistic creation methods, but the most fundamental, critical, and reliable method is to take root in the people and take root in life."^② General Secretary Xi's speech has a healthy and harmonious socialist literature and art. Prosperity and development have important guiding significance for building a modern socialist cultural power.

Music creation is a kind of artistic practice, which refers to the complicated mental production labor of composers to create music with musical beauty. People's musician Shi Guangnan's song creation has a strong life atmosphere, sincere feelings, warm and cordial. "People's character" is the primary principle in his creation. He is rooted in the masses of the people, well acquainted with the aesthetic needs of the masses, and always adheres to the direction of "serving the people". The song materials are taken from the people and used by the people. Comrade Xi Jinping believes that "socialist literature and art are essentially people's literature and art."

③

In the new historical period, it is extremely necessary for the healthy development of Chinese songs to continuously explore and dig out the "people's character" of music creation, to explore and study the melody thinking with Chinese style and Chinese charm and the beautiful and moving beauty of singing.

1. The creative road of people's musician Shi Guangnan

People's musician Shi Guangnan has created more than a thousand music works (parts) of various genres in his lifetime. The special environment makes great musicians. In his creation, there is passionate revolution, lyricism of shallow singing, rooted folk nationality, fashion-leading timeliness, all-inclusive artistry, and mass nature of sharing with the people. His creative thoughts and his creative process all reflect what is a people's musician.

Shi Guangnan's music creation is always passionate and full of passion. If it is divided by the stage of creation, it can be divided into two stages before and after China's Cultural Revolution.

Shi Guangnan's Music Creation in the Early Period of "Cultural Revolution"

Shi Guangnan was born in a revolutionary family. From the perspective of the inheritance of music, it seems that there is not much involvement. However, Shi Guangnan has an indissoluble bond with music since

childhood and has shown musical talent, often composing and singing by himself. At the age of 5, Shi Guangnan composed his first song: "Spring is here, the peach blossoms are red, the birds fly, and the yellow warblers are calling on the tree. They are happy, I am happy too, everyone is happy!" ④ This song was memorized by Shi Guangnan's attentive mother, and it was also named "Spring". In middle school, Shi Guangnan officially started his dream of composing. In high school, he became more obsessed with music creation and published his first edition collection. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, he entered the Composition Department of the Central Conservatory of Music. After graduating from university in 1964, he was assigned to Tianjin Musical Opera.

As a creator of the Academy, Shi Guangnan was transferred to the Beijing Central Orchestra in 1978.

The latter part of this period is the growth stage of Shi Guangnan's music creation. Produced some representative works, such as: "Revolutionary Martyrs' Poems" vocal tunes, "Ruili Riverside" violin solo and the song "Play the drums and sing songs", etc.

Shi Guangnan's Music Creation in the Late Period of "Cultural Revolution"

The political movement of the "Cultural Revolution" of ten years of catastrophe finally ended in 1976. Shi Guangnan's music creation also ushered in the spring. His heart is turbulent, full of affection, and his thoughts are flowing with infinite joy. During this period, he created a large number of excellent works. For example: "Toast Song", "Sentimental Land", "Play the drum and sing a song", "If You Want to Know Me", "White Feathers Send Affection", "Turpan's Grapes Are Ripe", "On the Field of Hope", etc. Wait. These heartfelt, tearful, cheerful, smooth, and lyrical melody embodies the spirit of the times of the people of the whole country at that time, and is a triumphant hymn for the people of the whole country to release their oppression and break the spiritual shackles. As a result, Shi Guangnan's songs quickly spread throughout the motherland, becoming the voice of the times and the voice of spirit.

2. The "people's character" of musician Shi Guangnan's song creation

The music creation of composer Shi Guangnan is full of passionate revolution, full of lyricism of shallow chanting, rich of rooted folk nationality, rich of modernity leading fashion, rich of all-inclusive artistry, rich of people's character of sharing with the people. The people's character of his song creation is mainly embodied in the strong national character, simple popular character, distinctive time character and strong family and country feelings. Shi Guangnan's music creation is always passionate and full of passion. His creative thoughts and his creative process all reflect what is a people's musician.

(1) Shi Guangnan's song creation has a strong national character

The songwriter Shi Guangnan's creation involves many fields, and his song creation has distinct characteristics of the times. His song creation technology inherits the past and the future, and has epoch-making special significance. The melody of his songs comes from the call of the people, rooted in the national folk music tradition, strong national atmosphere, appropriate artistic techniques, connotative artistic accomplishment, unique, creatively integrated and ingeniously created, forming song creation Strong national character.

"A composer, especially a Chinese composer, is extremely important to have strong national characteristics in addition to personal style characteristics." ⑤ His song creation, "Elegant and Popular, Appreciate Together", is deeply loved by the masses of people. He embodies the national characteristics of Shi Guangnan's song creation thought from various aspects such as national style, creative technique, musical form, aesthetic characteristics, and creative thought. His creative thought has produced a positive and far-reaching influence on the entire era. Influence.

Shi Guangnan has studied the folk music of various ethnic groups in our country, integrated and creatively used it. He has a detailed knowledge and deep love for Chinese folk music. Shi Guangnan's song creation is usually not quoting or copying the tunes of specific folk songs of various ethnic groups. He first studied, digested, mastered, skillfully used the characteristics and charm of national folk music, and at the same time, he continued to study national folk music deeply, grasping characteristics, finding patterns, combining the style of the times, creating unique melody with distinctive national characteristics, and dare to Boldly learn from other excellent music cultures in the world.

Shi Guangnan devoted himself to the study of national folk music, and he was keen to learn national folk music. "In addition to folk songs, I also learn a variety of rap music, and can imitate a variety of different local styles and the charm of Chinese characters to sing" ⑥. The creative conception of the song dare to imitate and boldly integrate the local characteristics of the regional folk music tonal structure characteristics, and emphasize the national characteristics of the song. For example: "Lazy Dunia" and "Lover's Dialogue" created in the early days; "Tian Zi scolds Tian Gong" in the east of Guangdong style, "Send the Good News Home" with the flavor of Jidong, and "The Most Beautiful Hymn" in the Korean style. Dedicated to the Party", Xinjiang Uyghur style "Play the drums and sing a song", Dai style "Phoenix tail bamboo under the moonlight" and so on.

The song "Turpan's Grapes Are Ripened" is one of Shi Guangnan's national masterpieces of song creation. The music conception is rooted in the distinctive rhythm and tones of Uyghur folk music, using modern composition techniques, and continuously developing musical thoughts on the theme and motivation of the music, emphasizing the national color of the song.

吐鲁番的葡萄熟了

开阔、自由地

翟琼词
施光南曲

The introduction of the song is a common introduction in Xinjiang Uyghur singing and dancing. This piece of music has a broad and far-reaching artistic conception. Using music to show the beautiful Tianshan Mountains, dense jungles, and the green Turpan Grape Valley, a picture of the Uighur's grand harvest season and a happy life.

Immediately afterwards, a split-tone rhythm with distinctive Uyghur flavor characteristics, coupled with a typical Uyghur tambourine ensemble, appeared in tandem, creating an exciting love scene in which a pair of Uighur young men and women admiring each other. Based on the characteristic cheerful rhythm, Shi Guangnan made the motivation, and continued to develop the theme of the song through continuous upward and downward modelling, timely modification, and spatial shifting.

The composer of this song used his own unique ideas and cleverly used elements of Xinjiang folk songs to seamlessly integrate into the general rules of song creation. Mr. Shi Guangnan pioneered the organic combination of the charm of Uyghur music and modern composition thinking, from the musical tone, the development of melody, the use of rhythm to the structure and distribution, etc., and creatively created sinicized, unique ethnic styles of Xinjiang Uyghurs. Easy to sing and easy to remember classics.

In the song creation of the composer Shi Guangnan, the folk tones of a specific region and nation are broken down and divided according to the specific connotation and artistic conception of the lyrics, and the local characteristics and national sentiments are subtly integrated with the thoughts and emotions of the lyrics. The typical tunes of specific ethnic and local characteristics give people a novel and unique aesthetic experience, which arouses strong resonance from the viewers.

The artisticization of national songs and the nationalization of art songs are also the practical pursuit of the composer Shi Guangnan's artistic creation of songs. The song art of each of the 56 ethnic groups in our country has a long history and has its own heritage. In the process of his creation, he worked hard to practice the artisticization of national songs. For example: songs "Amei's Heart", "Waiting at Twilight", etc. These are both popular and smooth and beautiful in melody, which fits the public's perspective, and they love to hear and be accepted by the public.

(2) Shi Guangnan's song creation is simple and popular

The composer Shi Guangnan always puts "popularity" in the first place in the creation of songs. "Mass, people, and groundedness" are the outstanding features of his works. "The artisticization of mass songs, the massification of art songs" ⑦. The basis of "massification" is to organically integrate the folk, the people, and the people's music materials, and create based on the people's "integration" and "comprehensive innovation".

For example: the creation of the song "Toast Song".

In October 1976, the Party Central Committee implemented the will of the party and the people and took drastic measures to completely smash the "Gang of Four". The 10-year civil strife of the "Cultural Revolution"

longing expressed the sincere praise and deep condolences of the older generation of revolutionaries who contributed their lives to the revolutionary cause by the broad masses of China at that time.

Shi Guangnan is a passionate and romantic creator. These songs sang the joys, sorrows and sorrows of hundreds of millions of people, truly expressed the aspirations of the people, and aroused the strong sympathy of hundreds of millions of people. He said: "I feel the resonance that arises when the feelings of an author communicate with the masses. My creation has been melted with the hearts of the people. This is the happiest thing. I realized from this that there is only truth in music works. Only by deeply embodying the feelings of the broad masses of people can they have strong vitality and eternal value." ⑨

His song creation is rooted in the masses of the people, often from the perspective of the masses, sincere feelings, direct expression of ideas, directly hit the bottom of the people's hearts, it is easy to arouse strong resonance among the people. Always encourage me to sing in a natural and bright voice. Most of the songs he composed are natural, fresh, affectionate and persistent, full of atmosphere, and have a strong sense of the times. They penetrate the grassroots and are close to the people's hearts. They are models of modern and contemporary Chinese song art and are deeply engraved in the history of Chinese art song creation. Because of his roots in the people and the people's lives, many of his songs were quickly sung throughout the country as soon as they appeared. From these songs, the people feel the value of their own existence, and everyone thinks that they are the songs in their hearts.

(3) Shi Guangnan's song creation has a distinctive timeGeneration

The songs composed by the composer Shi Guangnan not only have a strong national character and a broad mass character, but also have a strong sense of the times. They penetrate the grassroots and are close to the people's hearts. They are a model of Chinese modern and contemporary song art. This distinctive contemporary character Features are deeply engraved in the annals of the creation of Chinese art songs.

People's musician Shi Guangnan always integrates himself into the motherland in song creation, is closely connected with the people, deeply expresses the people's feelings, expresses the people's aspirations everywhere, and engraves the distinctive imprint of the times. Songs such as "On the Field of Hope", "Sentimental Land", and "Toast Song" are not only the sonorous declarations of the times, but also the inner monologues of the composer's strong sense of responsibility and mission. Shi Guangnan inherited and developed the excellent traditions of revolutionary music initiated by Nie Er and Xian Xinghai. As a composer cultivated by New China, the party's literary and artistic thought has a profound influence on him, and his song creation has a distinctive contemporary character. Li Xu said: "Just like 'Wen is like a man,' Shi Guangnan's creation can stand at the forefront of the times and show a healthy and upward spirit. His works have also become the 'spokesperson' of the spirit of the Chinese people." ⑩

The song "On the Field of Hope" is an optimistic and progressive song of the times that stands at the forefront of the times and is permeated with the atmosphere of the times and national customs. The song was created in the early stage of reform and opening up. The Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee of the Party drew up a beautiful blueprint for the comprehensive reform of China's rural areas; the strong sounding of the party's reform and opening horn quickly ignited the skyrocketing enthusiasm and labor enthusiasm of farmers, and also greatly ignited the fields. Hope. At that time, China's rural areas were carrying out the rural economic reform of "contracting with production and contracting production to households". Farmers saw new hope from the new policy, and the productivity was greatly liberated.

The song "On the Field of Hope", composed by Shi Guangnan and composed by Chen Xiaoguang, is a lyrical song with a lively rhythm, unrestrained human sentiment and distinctive characteristics of the times. The lyrics and melody are truly harmonious and complement each other. , Is a song that sings the prosperity and strength of the motherland, and it can be called a classic in the history of music.

The song "On the Field of Hope" reflects the beginning of the 1980s. From the prelude of the song, we can feel the vigor and prosperity of the whole society. It expresses the young generation's expectation for reform and longing for the future. The breath of the times. The song has a local flavor, the lyrics are simple, the tune is beautiful and smooth and catchy. Coupled with the youthful and affectionate interpretation of the song by the singer Peng Liyuan, it immediately aroused a great response and quickly spread across the country.

在希望的田野上

1 = $\flat$ B $\frac{2}{4}$

十大作曲家施光南作品选 (18)

晓光作词
施光南作曲
岭上松制谱

中快 活力 朝气蓬勃地

(殷秀梅 演唱)

mp 明朗地

(5 6 5 3 5 | 5 6 5 3 5 | 5 6 5 3 5 5 | 3 4 3 2 3 | 2 3 2 1 2 3 5 | 1 0 $\overset{35}{\underset{c}{i}}$) |

5 1 2 | 3. 4 3 2 | 3 - | 3 5 | 5 2 4 | 3 2 2 5 | 2 3. 5 | 1. 0 |

我 们 的 家 乡 在 希 望 的 田 野 上;
我 们 的 家 乡 在 希 望 的 田 野 上;
我 们 的 家 乡 在 希 望 的 田 野 上;

3 2 3 | 2 6 7 2 | 7 7 6 7 | 6 5 | 5 3 5 3 | 2 2 3 2 1 | 1 6 0 1 | 2 - |

炊 烟 在 新 建 的 住 房 上 飘 荡, 小 河 在 美 丽 的 村 庄 旁 流 淌。
禾 苗 在 新 农 民 的 汗 水 里 抽 穗, 牛 羊 在 牧 人 的 笛 声 中 成 长。
人 们 在 明 媚 的 阳 光 下 生 活, 生 活 在 人 们 的 劳 动 中 变 样。

5 5 5 | 5. 2 3 4 | 3 2 3 | 3^V 2 3 | 5 2 3 5 | 3 2 3 2 7 | 2 6 7 6 5 | 6 - |

This song uses folk song elements and combines the rhythm of the march. It has the rough and unrestrained folk songs of the north and the beauty of the south folk songs. At the same time, it loses the opportunity to integrate into the lively celebration of folk gongs and drums, and the music is cheerful and smooth. By praising the hopeful fields of hometown, he expressed his praise of the good life, praised the new life, and praised the new era. This fresh, natural and rustic song sings the vigorous and prosperous scene of China's rural reform and opening up, and sings the common voice of the Chinese people towards a better future. "On the Field of Hope" has become contemporary China since its birth. Symbol of spiritual outlook ⑪.

"Play the drums and sing the song" is a song with strong ethnic flavor. Because this song is very catchy, it is the most popular among the people. For a while, people can hear this song humming all over the country. Although it is a good piece. However, due to the current political situation in China in the early 1960s, the promotion of this song was still met with great resistance. The upright Shi Guangnan was not afraid of hardships and dangers. He dared to speak up for his works, bravely fight, and stood up to the forefront of the times. Finally, he used songs and artistic creations to show the healthy and upward spirit of the entire society at that time. In this sense, he is a singer who leads the era, a pioneer soldier of the era, and a people musician of the era. His songs are indisputably contemporary.

People's musician Shi Guangnan always cleverly conforms to the tide of the times, uses his own unique artistic creations, and uses his works to strive to influence the entire era. The new era made Shi Guangnan, and Shi Guangnan's artistic creation also influenced and led the times. His song creation has become an important vane of new music creation since the new era of contemporary China, and it has also opened a new era of artistic creation.

(4) Shi Guangnan's song creation has a strong sense of family and country

Composer Shi Guangnan has never forgotten that he is "the son of the people" in his short life. Regardless of content or form, his song creation uses "nationality," "popularity," and "epochal" artistic pursuits, and always puts the "people" first, composes the songs of the people, and expresses the feelings of the people. His works are derived from the love for the motherland and the people; his works are derived from the people, from the heart and soul. Shi Guangnan loves the people, sings the people with music, and uses the lyricism and singing that the masses love to condense the national customs, patriotism, and spirit of the times into a strong and deep "family and country feeling."

1. Composer Shi Guangnan's "home" feelings from life and from the masses

Shi Guangnan began to prepare for his musical life when he was a teenager. He always used his spare time to copy songs, sing songs, and listen to songs. The accumulation of these materials originated from life and taken from the people. Constantly creating song melody, loved to hear, is popular, and laid a solid mass foundation for his composing road. Shi Guangnan's early manuscript "The Collection of Chinese and Foreign Songs" is a summary of the "music dream" of Shi Guangnan's middle school period.

When he was in college, Shi Guangnan's songs have made waves in the Chinese music industry and have been highly praised by the big names in the industry. The song "Five Good Red Flowers Send Home" attracted everyone's attention at the time and won the love of the masses.

This is a song to support the army widely circulated in the 1960s. The song fits the times, is catchy, and has a unique style. It is a work by the grassroots during Shi Guangnan University. Lu Ji, the former chairman of the Chinese Musicians Association, said: "The author of a time has the style, spirit, and tone of the time...Shi Guangnan's works reflect the optimism, health, and sunny atmosphere of a generation." ⑫ Song "Five Good Red Flowers Send Home"

欢快地

(6 5 6 5 3 7 | 6 5 6 5 3 7 | 6 6 1̇ 6 5 | 3 3 5 3 2 | 1 1 2 1 7 |

||: 6 · 1 5 | 6 - | 6 6 5 3 5) | 6 5 6 5 | 3 3 1̇ | 6 5 3 | 2 1 6 |

1. (齐) 春风 吹开 遍 地 花 哟 喂,
2. (齐) 老爹 爹他 把 言 发 哟 喂,
3. (齐) 妈妈 一旁 说 了 话 哟 喂,
4. (姐) 大姐 拿出 一 本 书 哟 喂,
5. (妹) 两个 妹妹 一 起 说 了 话 哟 喂,
6. (齐) 小伙儿 参军 离 开 了 家 哟 喂,

2 - | 2 3 · 5 | 3 5 1 7 | 6 - | 2 · 3 5 | 3 1 7 | 6 6 7 6 | 5 6 2 |

1. 吹 开 那 遍 地 花, 小 伙儿 参 军 就 要 离 开 家 呀,
2. 他 把 那 言 来 发, (父) 到 了 部 队 要 听 首 长 的 话 呀,

Shi Guangnan's music creation always takes the people as the source of music creation. His creation praised ordinary workers and builders at the grassroots level. In music creation, ordinary working people are used as the artistic image of Acura. Express your mind, appropriately, and show the lives of these ordinary working people from different sides, such as the songs "How Beautiful is Life", "If You Want to Know Me", etc. These are well-known and widely circulated masterpieces. Shi Guangnan uses his music to express the thoughts of ordinary laborers, their emotions, their lives, their love, and their happiness, anger, sorrow, and joy. Therefore, his songs are the endorsement of the people.

Shi Guangnan's song creation is from a different perspective, expressing the love, friendship and yearning for happiness in people's lives. In his song creation, he combines the requirements of society and the times, together with the expression of personal inner emotions, and naturally blends the feelings of the people with the self-feelings of the artist, and uses his own artistic creation techniques, mass music language, The contemporary spiritual temperament expresses the most extensive "home" feelings of musicians.

2. Composer Shi Guangnan is full of affectionate feelings of the country

General Secretary Xi Jinping's speech at the symposium on literature and art work incisively discussed patriotism and spoke highly of national sentiments. He pointed out: "Among the core values of socialism, the deepest, most fundamental, and most eternal thing is patriotism."¹³

Shi Guangnan is a composer who grew up with New China, and his music practice is closely related to New China. He has deep feelings for the new China, the new society, and the Communist Party of China. Shi Guangnan's song creation has sincere emotions, beautiful melody, exquisite and meticulous interludes, preludes, and close integration with the lyrics, which appropriately express the emotions of the song. His song creation portrays the broad life of the people and eulogizes the national style of the people of all ethnic groups. The music melody contains rich thoughts and emotions, full of deep love for the motherland and the people. He is a people's musician with a strong sense of responsibility and mission, and a great patriot.

Musician Sun Shen believes: "Shi Guangnan is a composer cultivated and grown up in New China. The party's literary and artistic thought has an important influence on him. His creative achievements are precisely obtained under the guidance of this correct creative thought. It is said that Shi Guangnan has inherited and developed the excellent tradition of revolutionary music initiated by Nie Er and Xian Xinghai."¹⁴ People's musician Shi Guangnan often acts as an ordinary worker in song creation, expressing his true feelings and loving the people. It is evocative to embody the true feelings. He is also a romantic composer, always full of passion and moving. His creation has great patriotism and expresses the common aspirations of hundreds of millions of people.

Representative works are:

"The Toast Song" has a cheerful and smooth melody, which is a lyrical song with distinctive characteristics of the times. When singing, there must be not only cheerful emotions, but also excitement and joy after reading the vicissitudes of life, and highlight the deep and heavy creative artistic conception that the composer wants to express.

The melody of "My Motherland Mother" is affectionate and beautiful, simple and unpretentious. It expresses the wandering, thousands of foreign children, and the strong nostalgia for the mother of the great motherland.

我走遍海角天涯，
我走遍海角天涯，

忘不了祖国妈妈，
忘不了祖国妈妈，
祖国妈妈呀，祖国妈妈呀，
祖国妈妈呀，祖国妈妈呀，

儿女在海外漂流，常思念久别的老家，
出走时满头青丝，归来时满头银发，
多少次
却依然

托怀着赤子之心，
捎给你深情的心，
献给你不谢的花。
你你

The melody of "The Amorous Land" is ups and downs deep, expressing the deep nostalgia for the hometown, and the strong rustic feeling is deeply moving.

我深深地爱着你，这片多情的土地，我
我深深地爱着你，这片多情的土地，我

踏过的路径上，阵阵花香鸟语；
时时都吮吮着，大地母亲的乳汁，
我耕耘过的田野上，你
我天天都接受着，你

层层金黄翠绿，我怎能离开这河叉山脊，
这河叉山脊，这河叉山脊。
这山路小溪，这山路小溪。

啊！
啊！
我我

The song "On the Field of Hope" has a lively and lively melody, moderately stretched rhythm, and full of sincere passion. It depicts the new face of the new socialist countryside, exudes a strong and fragrant local flavor, and reproduces the optimistic and positive spirit of the people across the country. Conveyed the aspirations of the people across the country...

Shi Guangnan always connects his creation closely with the fate of the motherland and the feelings of the people. The songs he composed all expressed his sincere love for the motherland and the people, and his infinite vision for the beautiful future of the motherland. At different historical junctures, he expressed the voice of the people and left the traces of the times.

Conclusion

People's musician Shi Guangnan is an important composer who grew up in New China, and his music works are universally loved by the Chinese people. His song creation is rooted in the treasure house of traditional Chinese music, and he boldly absorbs and draws on the excellent music of various nations around the world. His music creation has always been permeated with the lofty sentiment of loving the people of the motherland and loving socialism.

General Secretary Jin Ping proposed that "to regard the people as the main body of the performance of literature and art", which requires that "art and literature should reflect the aspirations of the people" and "learn from the people and life with an humility, and learn from the great practice and colorful life of the people. Absorb nourishment, continue to accumulate life and art, and continue to discover and create beauty." ¹⁵

Shi Guangnan is a talented, hardworking composer. In his short lifetime, he wrote thousands of songs (including vocal music, instrumental music, opera, dance drama, etc.). His works have a wide range of subjects and different styles. They have praises and praises to the motherland and the party, and they truly and delicately express the people's working life and spiritual feelings, and show all aspects of life. His creation is entirely for the people and for the motherland. He sings enthusiastically to thousands of Chinese people, and he contributes

everything he has to the artistic work of "serving the people". He publicly declared that his creative ideal is to use music to "express the voice of thousands of people." With his practical actions, he practiced the most extensive "people's character" in song art creation.

Deeply cherish the memory of the composer Shi Guangnan and pay tribute to the people's musician Shi Guangnan.

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